

Section 1.

Final Report for

The Honey Creek Targeted Watershed Project

U.S. Environmental Protection Agency Assistance ID No. WS-00E39901-0

Integrated Project Summary

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April 10, 2014

Section 1. Integrated Project Summary

I. Project History

The Honey Creek Targeted Watershed Program Proposal was submitted to US EPA Region 5 in November 2006. The abstract for the proposal stated

Water resource protection efforts since the early 1980s in the Honey Creek Watershed and other northwestern Ohio agricultural watersheds have focused on reducing the export of suspended solids and particulate phosphorus to Lake Erie, primarily through the use of conservation tillage. Tributary monitoring programs show that successes in reducing particulate pollutants have been accompanied by increased export of both dissolved reactive phosphorus and nitrate, which pose threats to Lake Erie and public water supplies, respectively. Meanwhile, TMDL studies have revealed the need to address impaired biological communities, especially in the headwater streams of Ohio's agricultural watersheds.

In this project, strategies outlined in the state-approved Honey Creek Watershed Action Plan will be implemented. These include sets of BMPs that simultaneously address the causes of both the increased dissolved nutrient export and the impaired biological communities. BMP targeting will be adjusted to maximize reductions in soluble phosphorus export. Program outputs will be measured in terms of acres, types, and locations of BMPs adopted while environmental outcomes will be measured through a continuation of pollutant export studies and initiation of a stratified sampling program to assess stream habitat and biological community recovery.

The proposal was selected for funding under a cooperative agreement with EPA Region 5. The project began on 01/01/2008 and, with a one year extension, extended for 6 years through 12/31/2013. Participants in the project included staff of Heidelberg University's National Center for Water Quality Research (NCWQR), the Seneca County Soil and Water Conservation District, the Sandusky River Watershed Coalition, the University of Toledo, and area farmers. The roles of each of these groups are described in Table 1. A detailed Quality Assurance Project Plan (QAPP) was submitted on 6/27/2008 covering all of the assessment methods, and it was subsequently approved on 6/12/2009. During the operation of the project 21 quarterly progress reports were submitted. These reports included copies of educational materials and power point presentations developed in connection with the project as well as BMP adoption maps.

Staff from Region 5 conducted an on-site review of the project on February 8, 2012. Reviewers seemed pleased with project progress, although no written review was received with comments, criticisms or recommendations.

II. Project goals

The specific environmental goals for the project included:

- (1) a reduction of total phosphorus (TP) export by 25%, and, through targeting dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) sources, a reduction of 35% in DRP export;
- (2) a reverse in the current upward trend of stream flashiness, as measured using the Richards-Baker Index (RBI) at the Honey Creek, Melmore U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) stream gage;

Table 1. Participants in the Honey Creek Targeted Watershed Project.

Participants	Role
Heidelberg NCWQR	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Project oversight, fiscal operations (issuing checks, financial records) 2. Farmer education regarding water quality issues. 3. Project outcome assessment regarding phosphorus export, stream flashiness, nitrate concentration exceedence, and stream habitats/macroinvertebrates
Seneca Soil and Water Conservation District	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Gain farmer applications for subsidized BMP implementation. 2. Use targeting criteria to select farmers for BMP subsidies and adjust subsidy rate. 3. Oversee farmer implementation of BMPs. 4. Distribute subsidy payments and track farmer cost sharing on fields receiving subsidies. 5. Hire and supervise project technician
Sandusky River Watershed Coalition	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Aid in educational programs associated with project.
University of Toledo	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Project outcome assessment with regard to relationship between stream habitat and fish communities in headwater streams
Honey Creek Farmers (>90 applicants)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Utilize BMPs on high risk fields. 2. Provide financial records for production costs on selected fields.

(3) a 50% reduction in the amount of time nitrate concentrations exceed the drinking water standard (10 mg/L nitrate-N) from a current average of 8.9% during 2000-2004 to 4.5% of the time during the last two years of the project period, as corrected for weather related variations in nitrate export.

An additional goal was to assess the degree to which successful upland erosion control programs would result in enhanced habitat conditions and related improvements in macroinvertebrate and fish communities in agricultural headwater streams. The streams selected were all under maintenance that provided for periodic sediment removal. We hypothesized that the reduced upland erosion rates would prolong the intervals between stream maintenance and thereby allow natural stream processes to create improved stream habitat.

III. Project outputs

The project outputs thought necessary to achieve the above goals were in the form of acreages of specific BMPs. Those BMPs, the projected acres, and the actual acres implemented are shown in Table 2. For the major BMPs included in the program aimed at reducing phosphorus loads, wheat planting fell short (projected 9,000 acres and realized 7,265 acre) while winter cover greatly exceeded its goal (1,500 projected and 5,338 realized). Farmer buy-in for nitrogen fertilizer reduction fell well short of its target (projected 3,050 acres and realized 490 acres). Other BMPs involved very small acreages, in terms of

Table 2. Projected outcomes and realized outcomes for specific BMPs.

Practice	Projected acres	Realized acres
1. Annual cover	1,500	5,338
2. Wheat planting	9,000	7,265
3. Hay planting	300	28
4. Nitrogen fertilizer reduction	3,050	490
5. Controlled Drainage	300	-
6.* Grid sampling and variable rate P fertilization	0	97

targeted and realized acres. Furthermore, many additional acres of winter cover crops have been adopted in the watershed, based on a growing awareness of the benefits of cover crops in improving soil health.

A very important component of the implementation program was that field selection was based on their risk for DRP export. Factors included in the risk scoring for each field included its proximity to a stream, slope factor, and phosphorus soil test levels in the top 2 inches of soil. Thus, these acres were deemed to be critical source areas, based on information available at the time the project was initiated.

Bret Margraf, an employee of the Seneca County Soil and Water Conservation District, served as the project technician. Bret received an award as **the Outstanding Area 1 Employee (2013)**. **He and his father also won the Outstanding Conservation Farmer for Ohio in 2012 and Ohio No-Till Farmer of the Year in 2011**. Bret has summarized his approaches and experience as the project technician in Section 2 of this report.

The project directly affected a total of 13,218 acres or about 13.9% of the approximately 95,000 acres in the watershed. And the areas affected were targeted to fields deemed most vulnerable to nutrient runoff. Many additional acres of cover crops were also adopted in the watershed, in part due to the educational programs of the targeted watershed project.

IV. Project Outcomes

Were environmental outcomes, as stated in the project goals, met by the project outputs? Goals 1 and 2 relating to P export and flashiness clearly were not met, but goal 3 to reduce nitrate was met (Report Section 3). In fact TP exports were 169% higher during the 6 years of the project (2008-2013) than during a previous 6 year period (2001-2006) and DRP exports were 173% higher. Stream flashiness either continued to increase or level off, but it did not appear to decline (Section 3, Figure 4). However, nitrate export dropped 92% relative to 2001-2006 (Report Section 3, Table 3), and exceedencies of the drinking water standard dropped more than 50% (Section 3, Table 5), indicating that the goal for nitrate concentration was met.

The outcomes of the studies of macroinvertebrate and fish communities in 20 maintained agricultural ditches are detailed in sections 5 and 6, respectively. As predicted, we found that habitat complexity in maintained ditches does increase gradually over a period of years after they are dredged (sections 5 and 6). The habitat quality of a maintained ditch was shown to be influenced by the ecoregion in which it is located, with ditches in higher gradient topography tending to have higher habitat quality than those in flat terrain (Section 5). Accordingly, the biotic integrity of the fish communities was significantly higher in morainal streams than in lake plain sites (Section 6). However, topography (ecoregion) and number of years since a ditch was dredged did not have clear effects on macroinvertebrate community structure (Section 5).

Over four summers the 20 ditches yielded over 160 kinds of macroinvertebrates and 35 species of fish, and numerous species of macroinvertebrates and fish reproduced in the ditches. Fish species richness was positively correlated with stream heterogeneity and was negatively correlated with total plant cover. Species richness of young-of-year (YOY) fishes was positively correlated with horizontal stream heterogeneity, while no relationship was detected between YOY species richness and vertical heterogeneity or percent plant cover (Section 6). In effect, each ditch presented a unique combination of habitat conditions that directly influenced the composition of the biological community.

One goal of this Targeted Watershed study was to assess the degree to which successful upland erosion control programs would result in enhanced habitat conditions and related improvements in macroinvertebrate and fish communities in agricultural headwater streams. However, ditch maintenance appears to exert an overriding influence on overall ditch habitat quality even after several decades and to mask the effects of BMPs applied to the land. BMPs may exert secondary impacts individually and in aggregate, but neither the aggregate nor individual effects of BMPs could be identified in this study.

V. Lessons Learned

The gap between project outputs and project outcomes contains a multitude of lessons regarding the complexity of documenting the benefits of BMP adoption at the watershed scale. Pollutant export, i.e., the tons of pollutants moving out of a watershed in a given year, is a consequence of four interacting factors:

1. The land resource base within the watershed upstream from the sampling station;
2. The land use, and related management practices associated with each land use;
3. The characteristics of the hydrological cycle for the watershed during that year;
4. Time lags in the movement of pollutants through the watershed/stream system upstream from the sampling station.

The land resource base for a watershed is, for practical purposes, a constant and can be described in terms of its soil types, topography and other geological factors, such a depth to bedrock, and karst areas. Information regarding the land resource base can be stored in GIS databases of varying levels of resolution, and forms the foundation of water quality modeling programs.

Land use in a watershed reflects how human societies use that land and the resource base it provides. The nature of the hydrological cycle also impacts land use. Given the land resource base and the regional climate regime, which is influenced by the hydrological cycle, land use in the Honey Creek Watershed is now dominated by row crop agriculture (~81%). Management practices associated with

each of the land uses in a watershed can change more quickly than the land uses themselves. The way farmers produce corn, soybeans and wheat in the Honey Creek Watershed has changed significantly during the past 40 years, while the change in row crop acres has changed little. The conditions of land surfaces that influence runoff in a given year reflect not only the management practices of that year, but also the cumulative effects of past management practices. For example, past applications of phosphorus in excess of plant removal can build up phosphorus soil test levels to high values that will influence phosphorus runoff for years to come.

The precipitation component of the hydrological cycle, as well as the runoff and stream flow it generates, are highly variable from year to year, although they do fall within statistical ranges for given rainfall regions. Nonpoint pollution is generated by the interaction of precipitation with land surfaces, resulting in both dissolved and particulate materials moving from land to stream networks and then to the tributary loading stations. Not all of the pollutants that move from land surface to streams in a given year necessarily move past the monitoring stations that year. This stream system storage can introduce time lags between changes in land management and related changes in pollutant export.

The pollutant load in any year represents the cumulative effects of the spatial distribution of interactions between the above factors across the upstream watershed. Signals from those interactions are reflected in both short-term and the long-term tributary loading data. For example, in October and November of 2011, wet weather prevailed such that farmers had limited time windows for broadcast applications of phosphorus fertilizers. Unfortunately, each “window” was followed by a runoff-inducing rainfall event. The signals from this combination of circumstances at the Honey Creek tributary loading stations consisted of extremely high DRP concentrations during those runoff events.

On an annual basis, there is a clear relationship between annual discharge and annual nutrient and sediment loads at tributary monitoring stations (Section 3, Figures 1-3). One reason average TP and DRP loads drastically increased is that average discharge from Honey Creek was 35% higher in 2008-2013 than in 2001-2006. Whether those differences simply reflect random or cyclical rainfall patterns or effects related to climate change is uncertain. In any case, the increased discharge during this study had a major impact on pollutant loads. Farmers have no control over the hydrologic cycle as it impacts their fields in a given year, yet rainfall has a dominating effect on pollutant export from their fields that year. Even 6-year averages are insufficient to account for the effects of variable precipitation.

Farmers can affect the flow weighted mean concentrations (FWMCs) of pollutants exported from their fields to a greater extent than the loads. Decreasing FWMCs will decrease loads, unless discharge increases more than FWMCs have decreased. Most BMPs are aimed at reducing concentrations of pollutants in runoff. The Honey Creek long-term data sets show that the FWMCs of suspended solids have undergone statistically significant decreases (Section 3, Table 2). Linear regression from 1977-2013 indicates a 45% reduction in FWMCs over the period of record, while sediment loads have decreased by 19%. Programs to foster adoption of no-till and reduced till crop production have been underway in the Honey Creek Watershed since the early 1980s. For approximately 70% of the soybean and wheat production in the watershed, farmers use no-till. Most corn is produced using deep vertical tillage, resulting in minimal cover. Neither no-till nor deep vertical tillage invert the soil, as moldboard plowing did in the past. Consequently phosphorus soil test levels increase at the soil surface, leading to increased DRP runoff.

The most dramatic changes in annual FWMCs in the long-term data sets for Honey Creek are for DRP (Section 3, Figure 2B). DRP concentrations dropped significantly from 1977 to the mid-1990s and then increased dramatically. These changes reflect the consequences of management changes adopted for both agronomic reasons and environmental reasons. The causes of the decreases and the subsequent increases are not fully understood, although it is certain that the decreases in the 1980s were not a product of intentional adoption of BMPs to reduce DRP export. Instead those decreases were a consequence of changes in management practices adopted for purely agronomic reasons. In particular, phosphorus fertilizer sales dropped during this period as farmers shifted from build-up towards maintenance rates of application. The causes of the very large increases in DRP export beginning in the mid-1990s are also not fully understood. Adoption of BMPs to reduce erosion, which were the basis of agricultural phosphorus control programs that accelerated in the 1990s, likely has caused some of the increases in DRP export. The potential for this trade-off between particulate and dissolved phosphorus controls was known in the early 1980s when the agricultural pollution abatement programs were being planned. Other changes in management practices, adopted for purely agronomic purposes were also likely contributors to increasing DRP runoff. **These assessment results indicate that whatever the causes are for the increased DRP runoff, they are still operating and possibly worsening in the Honey Creek Watershed. Similar increases are occurring in other agricultural watersheds of northwestern Ohio, although they are most pronounced in the Honey Creek Watershed.**

Although the goal to reduce nitrate concentrations was met, this was because of a combination of changes in nitrogen management adopted for agronomic reasons coupled with increased discharge. It had little to do with adoption of BMPs for environmental reasons.

These “lessons learned” are certainly not unique to this study, although this study provides excellent examples of the challenges in documenting watershed-scale benefits from BMP adoption. To reduce the export of a specific pollutant, such as DRP, the interactions of the dominant factors that influence that pollutant’s export must be understood. Then management practices must be changed at the watershed scale, such that measurable decreases in export can be detected at monitoring stations, even in the face of varying and changing rainfall patterns.

VI. Related Developments

Since the submittal of the Honey Creek Targeted Watershed Proposal in 2006, much related research has been done and many studies mounted. Conditions in the lake have continued to deteriorate. A partial list of these developments includes the following:

1. A Great Lakes Protection Fund grant to Heidelberg to study the extent of phosphorus stratification in area soils as a contributing factor to increases in DRP loading to Lake Erie. This grant operated over the same time frame as the Honey Creek Targeted Watershed Project. Synergies between these two projects greatly benefitted both projects.
2. The Ohio Lake Erie Phosphorus Task Force was assembled in 2007 by the Ohio EPA in consultation with Heidelberg NCWQR staff, to address the issues of increasing DRP loading to Lake Erie and the re-eutrophication of the Lake. The final report of that task force was published in 2010. Through those deliberations, additional contributing factors to the DRP increases were identified, including the role of tile drainage, increased broadcasting of P-fertilizer and soil compaction.

3. A suite of 7 research grants were issued by the EPA's Great Lakes National Program Office, in part as a consequence of the deliberations of the Ohio Lake Erie Phosphorus Task Force, dealing with phosphorus issues ranging from on-field, rainulator studies to in-lake phosphorus studies. Manuscripts from those projects are currently in various states of review by editors of the Journal of Great Lakes Research.
4. State agencies in Ohio re-convened the Ohio Lake Erie Phosphorus Task Force to specifically develop recommendations for methods to reduce DRP loading to Lake Erie. The report of that task force was published in 2013. Improving soil health through a combination of no-till production and cover crops was a major recommendation of the task force. The task force also recommended new sets of target loads to address the problem of harmful algal blooms in the Western Basin of Lake Erie. Those targets included specific targets for DRP.
5. The NOAA supported ECOFORE project centered at the University of Michigan, involved an inter-university, inter-agency team along with consulting firms to develop forecasting models regarding hypoxia in Lake Erie. That group is proposing revised phosphorus target loads for Lake Erie including specific targets for DRP.
6. The International Joint Commission and Great Lakes Science Advisory Board have initiated several studies regarding the re-eutrophication of Lake Erie, culminating in the publication entitled "A Balanced Diet for Lake Erie – Reducing Phosphorus Loadings and Harmful Algal Blooms" (February 2014).
7. The fertilizer industry has developed a set of guidelines for nutrient management that are built around the 4-Rs, i.e., the fertilizers should be applied at the right time, with the right placement, in the right amount (rate) and in the right form (source). This industry-led initiative mirrors NRCS recommendations but differs in its pathways of delivery to farmers.
8. Sets of paired edge-of-field runoff studies are being mounted in the Lake Erie Basin and adjacent areas where BMPs targeted to DRP reduction will be evaluated relative to their effects on both tile drainage and surface runoff.
9. The Heidelberg NCWQR recently hosted a research planning and coordination conference supported by its GLPF grant. This workshop involved researchers along the continuum from field to lake for information sharing and identification of research gaps.
10. In 2011, Lake Erie experienced its all-time largest blue green algal bloom on record. This has led to increasing pressure on the agricultural community to reduce phosphorus loading to the Lake.
11. In 2013, microcystin levels in lake water approached and, in some cases, exceeded safe drinking water levels set by the World Health Organizations. This situation has put additional pressure on state and federal agencies to do something about the phosphorus inputs that seem to be causing these algal blooms.

The above developments set the stage for moving forward with both management actions and a research strategy for addressing the problems of the re-eutrophication of Lake Erie. The time to act is now.

VII. Recommendations

1. A set of "no regrets" BMPs need to be identified and endorsed by all involved parties that will be amenable to farmer adoption, reduce DRP runoff, and not be accompanied by

undesirable side effects. These BMP's should take into account site specific needs and opportunities rather than a one-size-fits-all approach.

2. Implementation of those "no-regrets" BMPs needs to be financially supported as appropriate to their benefits and costs to all affected groups from farmers to lake users.
3. A scaled set of "research watersheds" needs to be established and maintained such that watershed-scale effectiveness of those BMPs can be evaluated in as short a time span as possible. This will allow larger scale implementation programs to proceed with the assurance that they will accomplish attainable goals and will not be accompanied by adverse trade-offs. Such a strategy will support timely inclusion of adaptive management procedures in the Lake Erie Watershed management programs.
4. As new and innovative BMPs are identified, they should be incorporated into management activities at the field and small watershed scales, so their utility can be assessed as quickly as possible.
5. These programs should be operated in conjunction with advanced models that can aid in targeting BMP implementation and in evaluating the effects of variable weather and precipitation patterns.

We believe that all parties in the Lake Erie Basin, ranging from those representing agricultural and environmental interests, governmental agencies at multiple levels, and the research community would be interested in advancing the above recommendations. At present, only pieces of the above are being pursued. We, the concerned public, lose time and efficiencies if these pieces are not integrated and gaps are not filled.

Section 2.

Final Report for

The Honey Creek Targeted Watershed Project

**U.S. Environmental Protection Agency Assistance ID No. WS-
00E39901-0**

**Targeted BMP Implementation:
Summary and Observations**

**(Prepared by Bret Margraf, Project Technician,
Seneca Soil and Water Conservation District)**

March 31, 2014

Summary of Work Completed

The start of the grant began almost eight months behind schedule. The start date for the technician had a lot to do with the delay. As a result the first year started in September, almost too late to get any practices to be established. The initial focus was education and buy in of fertilizer retailers; this was done for most of the first year and continued throughout the grant. Secondly, a meeting series for producers to educate them on the environmental concerns from current fertilizer practices and how they could benefit from the TWG lasted for about two years. During this time cold call visits to farm operations were common. Additional efforts were made to educate and build trust with both producers and retailers in the following ways:

- Education of farmers, landowners, retailers, bankers, and community about issues related to phosphorus export from production fields and the ramifications downstream from the movement of phosphorus.
- Provide information on the likeliness of best management practices to minimize the risk of phosphorus movement.
- Training methods included one on one farm visits, a series of breakfast meetings, field day events, bus tours to view bmp's, group bus trips to demonstration farms, informational direct mailings, brochures, newsletter publications, and train the trainer sessions.
- The most effective communication occurred while meeting with producers at their farm, in one-on-one conversations. This resulted in the greatest cooperation.
- Soil sampling across the watershed was used to determine the amount of nutrient stratification in the soil profile. The higher the nutrient concentration on the soil surface, the greater the chance for nutrient export from storm events.
- An advisory committee was organized and included three producers, three fertilizer retailers, two agricultural loan agents, NRCS representatives from each county, a representative from the National Center for Water Quality Research and the Sandusky River Watershed Coordinator. The group met annually to review the grant programs and progress in relationship to the current agricultural and economic environment. Any adjustment made throughout the grant was done with the consent of the advisory committee.

TASKS DONE TO ENCOURAGE ADOPTION

- Adoption was encouraged through economic information. Education was provided on the cost of nutrient loss to the producer and how best management practices could reduce those losses.
- Specific producers geographically spaced throughout the watershed were used as role models for success. The goal was for these specific producers to be examples of how well bmp's work, while the neighbors would watch and be assured of success with adoption.

- Best Management Practices with incentive payments included the following:
 - ***wheat planting after stratified soil test – 7265 acres***
This practice took minimal effort to implement and also served as a springboard into other bmp's. Several adjustments were made to mitigate P effects such as splitting the amounts of broadcast P between fall and spring or delaying fall application until crop emergence.
 - ***deep banding of nutrients after stratified soil testing – 247 acres***
A practice with zero adoption during the first three years, simply because no farmer or fertilizer dealer had any of the equipment needed. Several machines have since been purchased and an increasing number of acres are being applied with each season.
 - ***perennial hay planting after stratified soil testing – 28 acres***
This was a very limited bmp because of the declining number of animal units in the watershed. The current economic conditions are very favorable for grain production and not so much for hay production.
 - ***annual cover crop planting after stratified soil test – 5338 acres***
In year one, less than fifty acres of this bmp were put into practice. By the final year over fifteen hundred had been incentivized before funding elapsed. This number could have easily reached twenty five hundred acres. With funding I could have cover crops on three-fourths of the watershed in the next 3 years.
 - ***nitrogen release inhibitors – 490 acres***
A new trend in corn production is nitrogen stabilizers. Nitrogen use efficiency in corn can be as low as 50%. These new products slow the conversion to nitrate in unfavorable weather condition, thus keeping the nitrogen available for the plant and less susceptible to atmospheric or leaching loss. This bmp was used as a means to introduce stabilizers to a set of farmers that otherwise would have not invested in this practice. The ultimate goal is for an overall reduction of nitrogen fertilizer application in corn production.
 - ***nutrient management grid soil sampling with variable rate applied nutrients – 97 acres***
Most mid to high management producers have already adopted this practice. The late adopters should be the highest priority target; unfortunately they are also the hardest to persuade to make a change.

THOUGHTS AND OPINIONS

- In the early 1980's the promotion of no-till was extremely successful because the education component was on farm, one-on-one teaching. The TWG used that same premise to educate, as well as provide incentive payments along the way – a great tandem.
- Too much emphasis is placed on the amount of dollars spent on best management practices, and more emphasis needs to be on having the right people implement the program. Producers respect someone with “real world experience”; this opens the door for conversation which will lead to conservation.

CONTINUING PRACTICES IN WATERSHED

An emphasis was placed on outreach and education to fertilizer retailers. The premise was to get buy-in on the retail side and they would help deliver the message of responsible fertilizer use to the producer. Local retailers participated in education meetings, planning and advisory decisions for this and other grants and field day events. The fertilizer dealers had a significant impact in the success of the TWG grant and will continue to deliver, as well as exercise the message of responsible fertilizer use. There are some additional practices that are likely to continue after the grant has concluded:

- A number of producers have made capital investments into strip till machines with capabilities of deep placement of fertilizer. Because the investment dollars are so high for this equipment, the practices will likely continue for some time.
- The practice of cover cropping appears to be something here to stay. The TWG cost shared over sixteen-hundred acres of cover crops in the fall of 2013. Transect data in the Honey Creek Watershed indicate over three-thousand total acres of cover crop. That means after five years of promoting cover crops, there is now an equivalent number of acres being planted without any grant funding.
- Although it is not a practice, awareness and knowledge gained by the producers is something that can result in change. Mindfulness of the downstream effects is now a common consideration by many producers when planning and applying fertilizer.

COMPARISON OF PRACTICES IN AND OUTSIDE HONEY CREEK

Farm operation is not defined by -- or confined to -- a watershed; therefore, many of the producers who farm in the Honey Creek Watershed also farm outside the watershed boundary. As a result, many of the bmp's from the TWG are visible in surrounding areas as well.

- Recent infrared satellite images show a dramatic difference between the amount of land with cover in and around the Honey Creek Watershed as compared to area outside the watershed.

The TWG was one of the most successful grant programs ever administered by the SWCD for a multitude of reasons. First, it was simple: the bmp's were simple; the sign up and contracts were simple; and the payment was simple. This was important because many producers were getting fed up with bureaucracy of farm bill programs. They were cumbersome, required many trips to the government office to sign papers, and, worst of all, had unexpected changes in mid-contract. The TWG was simple.

Secondly, participation was very high, and many were repeat customers. Over 90 different applicants submitted for approval, on several hundred different units of land. This participation resulted in a ground swell of consciousness that stirred thoughts in producer's minds about the responsible way of applying nutrients, where the nutrients go when they leave the farm, how the nutrients impact others downstream and a genuine conservation mindset to their operation. Each meeting or field day seemed to invoke interest to new people. It became common place to think "wow, I never thought this guy would show up."

There are several things about the TWG I would welcome in a grant again, but the most important was the duration. Measurable change in agriculture does not happen in a year or two or three, it takes time. Producers can be described in three ways: early adopters, late arrivals, and late/resistant adopters; the last is a tough nut to crack. Early adopters are easy, but the late arrivals are the masses and they want to see things work with success before they bite. In order to get the late arrivals, three, four and sometimes five years are needed. This was evident in the TWG; the number of acres and participants swelled in the last couple of years.

Appendix 1. Adoption Maps

Figure 1. Cover crop adoption through the Honey Creek Targeted Watershed Project.

Figure 2. Participants in the Honey Creek Targeted Watershed Project.

Section 3.

Final Report for

The Honey Creek Targeted Watershed Project

U.S. Environmental Protection Agency Assistance ID No. WS-00E39901-0

Project Outcome Assessments, Part 1:

Chemical Loading and Hydrological Assessments

**(Prepared by Heidelberg University staff
under the direction of Dr. David Baker)**

March 31, 2014

List of acronyms and abbreviations

Chemicals

- SS – suspended solids
- TP – total phosphorus
- TPP – total particulate phosphorus
- DRP – dissolved reactive phosphorus

Others

- BMP- best management practices
- FWMC – flow weighted mean concentration
- HCTWP – Honey Creek Targeted Watershed Program
- NCWQR – National Center for Water Quality Research, Heidelberg University
- POR – period of record
- QAPP – Quality Assurance Project Plan
- RBI – Richards-Baker Flashiness Index
- USGS – United States Geological Survey

Section 3. Project Outcome Assessments, Part 1: Chemical Loading and Hydrological Assessments (prepared by Heidelberg University staff under the direction of Dr. David Baker)

The anticipated chemical and hydrological outcomes of implementing the Honey Creek Targeted Watershed Program (HCTWP) practices, as listed in the work plan, include

- (1) a reduction of total phosphorus (TP) export by 25%, and, through targeting dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) sources, a reduction of 35% in DRP export;
- (2) a reverse in the current upward trend of stream flashiness, as measured using the Richards-Baker Index (RBI) at the Honey Creek, Melmore U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) stream gage;
- (3) a 50% reduction in the amount of time nitrate concentrations exceed the drinking water standard (10 mg/L nitrate-N) from a current average of 8.9% during 2000-2004 to 4.5% of the time during the last two years of the project period, as corrected for weather related variations in nitrate export.

(1). Outcome Assessment: Reductions in TP export by 25% and DRP export by 35%...

a. Methods.

The monitoring program for the chemical and hydrological outcomes of the HCTWP is based on the NCWQR's tributary loading program. This program operates at 15 USGS stream gages in Ohio and one in Michigan (Krieger, 2014) and includes the USGS gaging station on Honey Creek at Melmore (see Appendix 1). In this report, the nutrient and sediment loading at the Honey Creek stations will be compared with loading from Rock Creek, a tributary to Sandusky River, from the Sandusky River at Fremont, and from the Maumee River at Waterville. The watersheds upstream from all of these stations are dominated by row crop agriculture. The sampling and analytical methods used in this program are described on the National Center for Water Quality Research (NCWQR) website (<http://www.heidelberg.edu/academiclife/distinctive/ncwqr/data>) and in the Quality Assurance Project Plan (QAPP) submitted for this project (Baker, 2009).

During water years 2008-2013, which coincide with the operation of this project, 3,169 samples were collected from Honey Creek for analysis of nutrient and suspended sediment export. Sampling was interrupted for ~ 6 months (8/14/2009 to 2/9/2010) due to bridge construction on SR 67/100 at Melmore, OH. The nature of the construction was such that the chemical sampling station that had been installed in 1976 had to be moved. A site 4.02 km "river km" upstream was selected for the new chemical sampling station. Since a significant tributary (Silver Creek) enters Honey Creek between these two locations, the drainage area upstream from the new sampling station was reduced by 20%. The land use in that 20% was essentially identical to the land use upstream from the USGS stream gaging site at Melmore. The USGS stream gaging station did not have to be moved. We will be assessing possible effects of the change in sampling location on our long term records for this site, using the SWAT model, after the model is revised to better incorporate the effects of tile flow on DRP export. It should be noted that for calibration of the SPARROW model, the USGS accepted data from chemical sampling

stations whose drainage areas ranged from 50% to 200% of the drainage areas at the nearest stream gage (SAAD et al., 2011). Consequently, the change in sampling location should have only minor impacts on loading calculations. Additional material regarding this change in sampling location will be posted on our tributary loading website.

b. Long-term trends in nutrient and suspended sediment export and concentrations

The long-term trends in annual discharge and in the annual export of nutrients and suspended sediments for Honey Creek provide a context for assessing changes in loads and concentrations during the HCTWP. The period-of-record (POR) for the Honey Creek monitoring station now includes 37 water years (1977-2013) during which 19,376 samples have been analyzed for nutrients and suspended sediments. As such, this station had the largest data set in the United States that was used by the USGS in the calibration of their SPARROW model (Saad et al., 2011). Our own analysis of these data sets includes calculation of annual loads for nutrient and suspended sediments, using an automated Beale Ratio Estimator program (Richards et al., 1996). The resulting annual loads (metric tons) divided by the annual discharges (million cubic meters) provide the annual flow weighted mean concentrations (FWMCs in mg/L) for each parameter. Plots of annual loads and FWMCs over the POR illustrate the long-term trends, or lack thereof, of nutrient and sediment export for Honey Creek (Figures 1-3).

Nonpoint source pollutant loading is characterized by large annual variations associated with annual variations in discharge (Figure 1). To illustrate the links between discharge and loading, a line graph of annual discharge is superimposed on the bar graphs of annual loading (Figures 1-3). The line graph superimposed on the FWMCs reflects a 5-year running average of the FWMCs (Figures 1-3). The strong links between discharge and loading are also reflected in regression analyses between various parameters (both loads and FWMCs) and discharge (Table 1). All of the relationships are statistically significant except for the regression of FWMCs for SS and TPP. It is noteworthy that for nitrate and chloride, loads are positively correlated with discharge while FWMCs are negatively correlated, and both sets of relationships are statistically significant. The probable explanation for this behavior for nitrate is that soils contain a limited pool of nitrate that is replenished annually by fertilizer, rainfall and nitrogen fixation. The pool size is relatively constant from year to year. While nitrate export at the Honey Creek station is higher in years of higher discharge, the higher discharges actually dilute the nitrate being exported, resulting in lower FWMCs. For chloride, a larger proportion of the load is derived from groundwater inputs than from storm runoff. Although chloride loads increase with increasing discharge, those increasing discharges from surface water actually dilute the chloride concentrations entering the stream from groundwater. The interpretation is supported by the small relative standard deviation of nitrate and chloride loads in comparison with the relative standard deviations of loads for SS, TPP and DRP (Table 2). For SS, TPP and DRP, the soils provide a large and essentially unlimited pool of erodible sediment with particulate phosphorus, as well as phosphorus available to move into runoff water as DRP. Thus increasing runoff increases loads more for these parameters than for nitrate and chloride. The low R^2 values for FWMCs of SS and TPP in relation to discharge (Table 1) are caused by the large effects of best management practices (BMPs) in reducing their FWMCs (Richards et al., 2009). These BMPs act independently of variations in annual discharge.

Figure 1. Period-of-record loading and concentration data for the Honey Creek Watershed as calculated at the USGS stream gage at Melmore, OH, including -- A) annual discharge, B) annual loads of suspended solids, C) annual FWMCs of suspended solids, D) annual loads of total particulate phosphorus, E) annual FWMCs of total particulate phosphorus. The line graphs superimposed on the loading graph reflect annual discharges and the line graphs superimposed on the FWMCs reflect 5-year running averages.

Figure 2. Period-of-record loading and concentration data for the Honey Creek Watershed as calculated at the USGS stream gage at Melmore, OH, including -- A) annual loads of dissolved reactive phosphorus, B) annual FWMCs of dissolved reactive phosphorus, C) annual loads of nitrate-N, D) annual FWMCs of nitrate-N, E) annual loads of chloride, F) annual FWMCs of chloride. The line graphs superimposed on the loading graph reflect annual discharges and the line graphs superimposed on the FWMCs reflect 5-year running averages.

Figure 3. Period-of-record loading and concentration data for the Honey Creek Watershed as calculated at the USGS stream gage at Melmore, OH, including -- A) annual loads of total phosphorus, B) annual FWMCs of total phosphorus, C) annual loads of total Kjeldahl nitrogen, and D) annual FWMCs of total Kjeldahl nitrogen. The line graphs superimposed on the loading graph reflect annual discharges and the line graphs superimposed on the FWMCs reflect 5-year running averages.

Application of simple regression analyses to POR data for Honey Creek, as presented in Figures 1-3, indicates that statistically significant increases of discharge and of loads and FWMCs of DRP have occurred (Table 2). Likewise, a statistically significant decrease in the FWMCs of SS has occurred over the POR. The end points of the regression lines for DRP show very large increases for loads (6.99) and FWMCs (2.98). The corresponding increase in discharge was 1.49. For TPP, nitrate and chloride, loads increased but FWMCs decreased over the period of record, although these changes were more moderate, and none of them were statistically significant. It is notable that SS loads decreased (0.81, final to initial) even though discharge increased (1.49).

Table 1. Relationships between annual loads and flow weighted mean concentrations and annual discharge for suspended solids, total particulate phosphorus, dissolved reactive phosphorus, nitrate-N and chloride over the period of record (1977-2013) at the Honey Creek Melmore sampling station, as reflected by simple linear regressions. The Coefficient of Determination (R-squared), P-value and slope sign are shown for each parameter and characteristic.

Parameter	Characteristic	Coefficient of Determination (R ²)	P-value	Slope sign
SS	load	0.35	0.0001	positive
	FWMC	0.02	0.37	positive
TPP	load	0.71	<0.0001	positive
	FWMC	0.08	0.09	positive
DRP	load	0.64	<0.0001	positive
	FWMC	0.26	0.0012	positive
Nitrate-N	load	0.24	0.0018	positive
	FWMC	0.43	<0.0000	negative
Chloride	load	0.71	<0.0000	positive
	FWMC	0.47	<0.0000	negative

c. Comparison of sediment and nutrient export during the project period with earlier time periods

It is clear that application of simple linear regressions to annual loads and FWMCs does not necessarily provide a best fit of the data. This is particularly evident for DRP loads and FWMCs, which clearly show decreases through the mid-1990s followed by even larger increases (Figure 1, D & E). Consequently, we have calculated average annual unit area loads and average annual FWMCs for four separate time intervals for Honey Creek and for three other agricultural watersheds (Tables 3 & 4). The time intervals include (1) 1976-1984 (9 years) that reflect conditions prior to the onset of erosion control BMPs through conservation tillage; (2) 1991-1998 (8 years) that reflect export conditions encompassing the period when Lake Erie was experiencing the largest reductions in eutrophication indicators; (3) 2001-2006 (6 years) that reflect the early years when Lake Erie was experiencing re-eutrophication; and (4) 2008-2013 (6 years) that reflect the period of continuing re-eutrophication of Lake Erie and the operation of the HCTWP. These particular time intervals were chosen by inspection of both tributary loading data and changing conditions in Lake Erie. The multi-year averages reduce, but do not eliminate, the effects of year-to-year variations in annual discharge on loads and FWMC.

Averages for the most recent period (2008-2013) are also expressed as percentages of the averages for each of the other three periods by dividing the 2008-2013 average by the other period averages (Tables 3 & 4). For example, average annual discharge for Honey Creek in 2008-13 was 137% of the corresponding average in 1976-84, 129% of the average in 1991-08, and 135% of the average in 2001-06. Large increases in average unit area discharge occurred between the 2008-13 period and the 2001-06 period in Honey Creek, Rock Creek and the Sandusky River, with much smaller increases in the Maumee River (Table 3). Rock Creek and Honey Creek are both tributaries to the Sandusky River. These

increases in discharge were accompanied by even larger increases in unit area export of SS, TP, DRP and TPP (Table 3). Average unit area loads of SS, TP, DRP and TPP also increased between 2001-06 and

Table 2. Time trends of annual discharge and of annual loads and flow weighted mean concentrations for suspended solids, total particulate phosphorus, dissolved reactive phosphorus, nitrate-nitrogen and chloride over the period of record (1977-2013) for the Honey Creek Melmore tributary loading station. Correlation coefficients r, P-values and the ratio of the final regression value (2013) divided by the initial regression value (1977) are shown. Statistically significant trends are shown in bold type and underlining.

Parameter	Characteristic	Relative Standard Deviation	Correlation Coefficient (r)	P-value	Final/Initial
Discharge	-	0.352	<u>0.334</u>	<u>0.0432</u>	<u>1.49</u>
SS	load	0.608	-0.102	0.5478	0.81
	FWMC	0.514	<u>-0.336</u>	<u>0.0419</u>	<u>0.55</u>
TPP	load	0.466	0.157	0.3540	1.28
	FWMC	0.275	-0.185	0.2721	0.84
DRP	load	0.774	<u>0.583</u>	<u>0.0002</u>	<u>6.99</u>
	FWMC	0.491	<u>0.609</u>	<u>0.0001</u>	<u>2.98</u>
Nitrate-N	load	0.271	0.172	0.3077	1.17
	FWMC	0.280	-0.163	0.3351	0.86
Chloride	load	0.253	0.172	0.3077	1.17
	FWMC	0.222	-0.060	0.7251	0.96

2008-13 for the Maumee, but these increases were smaller than those for the three Sandusky Watershed stations (Table 3).

In comparing 2008-13 loads as a percent of 1991-98 loads, DRP had much larger increases than any of the other parameters, with values of 390%, 343% and 323% for Honey Creek, Rock and the Sandusky River, and 175% for the Maumee. Increases in average discharge between these periods were 129%, 125% 128% and 107% for the Honey Creek, Rock Creek, Sandusky and Maumee stations. The much larger increases in loads than in discharges indicate that average annual FWMCs also had to increase substantially between these two periods, which is the case (Table 4). FWMCs of DRP in 2008-2013 were 302%, 275%, 252% and 164% of the 1991-98 values for these four rivers.

For all four rivers, nitrate FWMCs were lower during the 2008-13 than the other three time periods, and DRP concentrations were higher than in any of the other periods (Table 4). Thus flow weighted concentrations of DRP and nitrate are moving in opposite directions. For 2008-13, DRP unit area loads and FWMCs were higher in Honey Creek than in the other three long-term agricultural stations.

Another feature of the export data is the ratios of TPP/SS, which reflects the phosphorus “richness” of the suspended sediment (Table 3). Except for Rock Creek, the TPP/SS ratio has increased in successive time periods for each river. For 2008-13, the ratio of mg TPP/g SS for Honey Creek (2.40) is higher than ratios for the Rock, Sandusky and Maumee stations (1.58, 1.86 and 1.97, respectively). Ratios of DRP/TP in 2008-13 are also higher for Honey Creek (0.303), than for the other three rivers

Table 3. Comparison of average annual unit area discharge and yields of nutrients and suspended sediments for four agricultural watersheds during four periods (water years 1976-1984, 1991-1998, 2001-2006 and 2008-2013). TPP/SS ratios (mg/g) and DRP/TP ratios for each time period are also shown. The 2008-13 values are also presented as percentages of the previous three time periods.

River	Water Years	Discharge centimeters	Suspended solids kg/ha	Total phosphorus kg/ha	Dissolved reactive phosphorus kg/ha	Total particulate phosphorus kg/ha	Nitrate kg/ha	Total Kjeldahl nitrogen kg/ha	Total Nitrogen kg/ha	Chloride kg/ha	TPP/SS mg/kg ratio	DRP/TP ratio
Honey Creek	1976-84	31.6	655	1.35	0.236	1.12	15.3	5.33	19.8	62.6	1.71	0.175
Honey Creek	1991-1998	33.6	587	1.40	0.154	1.25	18.3	5.76	24.1	64.2	2.13	0.110
Honey Creek	2001-2006	32.3	345	1.17	0.347	0.83	18.8	5.06	23.9	79.5	2.40	0.296
Honey Creek	2008-2013	43.4	578	1.99	0.602	1.39	17.4	6.88	24.2	76.4	2.40	0.303
	2008/13/1976-84 as %	137%	88%	147%	255%	124%	114%	129%	122%	122%	141%	173%
	2008-13/1991-98 as %	129%	98%	142%	390%	111%	95%	119%	101%	119%	113%	275%
	2008-13/2001-06 as %	135%	167%	169%	173%	168%	92%	136%	101%	96%	100%	102%
Rock Creek	1976-1984	(not in operation)										
Rock Creek	1991-1998	34.7	1045	1.69	0.105	1.58	12.1	6.48	18.5	65.2	1.52	0.062
Rock Creek	2001-2006	29.5	612	1.22	0.235	0.98	12.4	4.89	17.3	77.4	1.61	0.193
Rock Creek	2008-2013	43.2	1135	2.15	0.360	1.79	11.2	7.92	19.2	78.4	1.58	0.167
	2008-13/1976-84 as %	(not in operation)										
	2008-13/1991-1998 as %	125%	109%	127%	343%	113%	93%	122%	103%	120%	104%	269%
	2008-13/2001-06 as %	146%	185%	176%	153%	182%	91%	162%	111%	101%	98%	87%
Sandusky R.	1976-84	35.3	842	1.58	0.287	1.29	16.1	5.38	20.8	91.1	1.53	0.182
Sandusky R.	1991-1998	34.8	721	1.45	0.137	1.31	19.2	5.86	25.1	82.4	1.82	0.095
Sandusky R.	2001-2006	34.2	567	1.33	0.303	1.02	20.9	5.65	26.5	100.5	1.80	0.229
Sandusky R.	2008-2013	44.5	815	1.96	0.442	1.52	18.8	7.22	26.0	99.7	1.86	0.226
	2008/13/1976-84 as %	126%	97%	124%	154%	118%	116%	134%	125%	109%	122%	124%
	2008-13/1991-98 as %	128%	113%	135%	323%	116%	98%	123%	104%	121%	102%	239%
	2008-13/2001-06 as %	130%	144%	148%	146%	149%	90%	128%	98%	99%	103%	99%
Maumee R.	1976-84	32.5	708	1.52	0.274	1.25	15.8	5.96	21.8	86.6	1.76	0.180
Maumee R.	1991-1998	33.2	675	1.39	0.188	1.20	19.3	5.63	24.9	83.9	1.79	0.135
Maumee R.	2001-2006	32.5	497	1.18	0.282	0.90	19.8	5.35	25.1	101.4	1.81	0.239
Maumee R.	2008-2013	35.5	574	1.46	0.329	1.13	16.2	6.20	22.4	86.2	1.97	0.225
	2008/13/1976-84 as %	109%	81%	96%	120%	91%	103%	104%	103%	100%	112%	125%
	2008-13/1991-98 as %	107%	85%	105%	175%	94%	84%	110%	90%	103%	111%	167%
	2008-13/2001-06 as %	109%	115%	124%	117%	126%	82%	116%	89%	85%	109%	94%

Table 4. Comparison of average annual flow weighted mean concentration of nutrients and suspended sediments for four agricultural watersheds during four periods (water years 1976-1984, 1991-1998, 2001-2006 and 2008-2013). The 2008-13 values are also presented as percents of the previous three time periods.

River	Water Years	Suspended solids	Total phosphorus	Dissolved reactive phosphorus	Total Particulate Phosphorus	Nitrate-N	Total Kjeldahl nitrogen	Total Nitrogen	Chloride
		mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L
Honey Creek	1976-1984	207	0.428	0.075	0.353	4.83	1.69	6.26	20
Honey Creek	1991-1998	175	0.418	0.046	0.372	5.45	1.72	7.16	19
Honey Creek	2001-2006	107	0.364	0.108	0.256	5.83	1.57	7.403	25
Honey Creek	2008-2013	133	0.458	0.139	0.319	4.00	1.58	5.579	18
	2008-13÷1976-84 as %	64%	107%	185%	90%	83%	94%	89%	89%
	2008-13÷1991-98 as %	76%	110%	302%	86%	73%	92%	78%	92%
	2008-13÷2001-06 as %	124%	126%	129%	125%	68%	101%	75%	71%
Rock Creek	1976-1984	not in operation							
Rock Creek	1991-1998	302	0.488	0.030	0.457	3.48	1.87	5.35	19
Rock Creek	2001-2006	207	0.413	0.080	0.333	4.19	1.66	5.85	26
Rock Creek	2008-2013	263	0.498	0.083	0.415	2.60	1.83	4.44	18
	2008-13÷1976-84 as %	not in operation							
	2008-13÷1991-98 as %	87%	102%	275%	91%	75%	98%	83%	96%
	2008-13÷2001-06 as %	127%	121%	104%	124%	62%	111%	76%	69%
Sandusky R.	1976-1984	238	0.446	0.081	0.365	4.57	1.52	5.88	26
Sandusky R.	1991-1998	208	0.417	0.039	0.377	5.53	1.69	7.22	24
Sandusky R.	2001-2006	166	0.387	0.089	0.298	6.10	1.65	7.75	29
Sandusky R.	2008-2013	183	0.441	0.099	0.341	4.22	1.62	5.85	22
	2008-13÷1976-84 as %	77%	99%	122%	94%	92%	107%	99%	87%
	2008-13÷1991-98 as %	88%	106%	252%	90%	76%	96%	81%	95%
	2008-13÷2001-06 as %	111%	114%	112%	114%	69%	98%	75%	76%
Maumee R.	1976-1984	218	0.468	0.084	0.383	4.87	1.83	6.699	27
Maumee R.	1991-1998	203	0.419	0.057	0.363	5.80	1.70	7.497	25
Maumee R.	2001-2006	153	0.364	0.087	0.277	6.08	1.65	7.73	31
Maumee R.	2008-2013	162	0.412	0.093	0.319	4.56	1.74	6.31	24
	2008-13÷1976-84 as %	74%	88%	110%	83%	94%	95%	94%	91%
	2008-13÷1991-98 as %	80%	98%	164%	88%	79%	103%	84%	96%
	2008-13÷2001-06 as %	105%	113%	106%	115%	75%	106%	82%	78%

(0.167, 0.226, and 0.225, respectively). The high DRP FWMC, TPP/SS ratios and DRP/TP ratios for Honey Creek may all be reflections of the same set of circumstances in this watershed. It is also noteworthy that the percent reduction in SS FWMCs between 1976-84 and 2008-13 is greater for Honey Creek (64%), than for the Sandusky and Maumee Rivers (77% and 74%, respectively) even though discharge increased more in Honey Creek (137%) than in the Sandusky and Maumee (126% and 109%, Table 3 & 4). These results may reflect greater adoption of erosion control measures in the Honey Creek

Watershed than in the Sandusky, as a whole, or in the Maumee watershed. Increases in DRP runoff are often associated with adoption of BMPs that decrease erosion and SS runoff (Kleinman et al., 2011).

d. Summary regarding TP and DRP load reduction outcomes

It is clear from the above discussions that the projected outcomes of the HCTWP relative to reducing TP export by 25% and DRP export by 35% have not been met. Discussion of these results is presented in Section 1 **Integrated Project Summary**.

2. Outcome assessment: A reverse in the upward trend of stream flashiness observed between the 1975 and 2001 water years ...

In the 1970s, Great Lakes tributaries were classified as “event response” and “stable response” rivers. For event response rivers, rainfall events trigger relatively large amounts of surface runoff into streams so that stream flows increase rapidly. These same streams frequently have low base flows. For stable response streams, rainfall events trigger more moderate increases in stream flow, with more percolation into the ground water systems. Stable response streams generally have greater baseflow. In general, event response rivers have much higher nutrient and sediment export rates than stable response rivers.

Our laboratory developed the Richards-Baker flashiness Index (RBI), wherein event response streams have high index values and stable response streams have low index values (Baker et al., 2004). The index can detect changes in flashiness associated with changes in land use/land management conditions. Application of that index, which is based on an analysis of day-to-day changes of stream flow at USGS stream gages, indicated that between 1975 and 2001, most rivers in Ohio were becoming flashier.

As part of the HCTWP, we have calculated RBI values for Honey Creek, the Sandusky River, the Maumee River, and Tymochtee Creek, another tributary to the Sandusky River with a long-term USGS stream gage. We substituted Tymochtee Creek for Rock Creek because discharge measurements for Rock Creek did not start until 1982. The RBIs for Honey Creek and Tymochtee Creek continue to be increasing while the RBIs for the Maumee and Sandusky River appear to be starting to decrease (Figure 4). This index may be useful in documenting watershed scale hydrological changes in response to improving soil health, the addition of water control structures to tile drainage, and/or the construction of wetlands in upland areas. To the extent that improvements in soil health increase water infiltration and the water holding capacity of soils (OEPA, 2013), the RBI could decrease. Although the linear regression between 2001 and 2013 appear to be offset lower than the 1977-2000 period, they still appear to be increasing in Honey Creek and Tymochtee Creek. At this time we have no explanation for why the RBI appears to have started to decrease in the larger watersheds (Maumee and Sandusky) while still increasing at the two smaller watersheds.

Figure 4. RBI Flashiness Index values from 1975 to 2013 for Honey Creek, Rock Creek, the Sandusky River and the Maumee Rivers. Linear equations, R², and P-values are shown for each river for the period from 1975 to 2000 and for 2001-2013.

3. Project Outcome Assessments: A 50% reduction in the amount of time nitrate concentrations exceed the drinking water standard of 10 mg/L nitrate-N...

The NCWQR tributary loading website contains a downloadable Excel macro program (AnalysisMonthlyV2) that provides automatic calculations and plots of concentration exceedency curves from the river data files that are also available on the website. One version of the program includes either comparisons of two rivers or comparison of a single river for two time intervals. The latter version of the program has been used to calculate and plot nitrate concentration exceedency curves for two periods (2001-2006 water years and 2008-2013 water years) (Figure 5). These time periods were chosen to coincide with two of the time periods included in Tables 3 & 4. The graphs indicate that the nitrate concentrations are lower at a given percent exceedency during the 2008-13 period than during 2001-06 (Figure 5). Also at a given concentration (e.g. 10 mg/L), the curves for 2008-13 fall to the left (lower percent exceedency) of the curves for 2001-06. These data indicate that for all four rivers, the percent of time nitrate exceeded its drinking water standard has decreased.

Between 2001-06 and 2008-13, the percent of time nitrate exceeded 10 mg/L decreased from 6.6% to 3.0% for Honey Creek, from 2.0% to 0.6% for Rock Creek, from 6.7% to 2.4% for the Sandusky River and from 5.8% to 0.9% for the Maumee River (Table 5). Percent exceedency for 12 mg/L and 8 mg/L also decreased between these two periods (Table 5). The decreasing nitrate concentration cannot be explained simply in terms of dilution of nitrate by increased discharge in these rivers, because unit area

Figure 5. Nitrate-nitrogen concentrations exceedency curves for Honey Creek, Rock Creek, the Sandusky River and the Maumee River for two time periods (2001-2006 and 2008-2013).

nitrate export also decreased in all four rivers. These data indicate that changing management practices are resulting in a lowering of nitrate concentrations in area rivers. We have not investigated the specific BMP or BMPs that are causing these reductions or the reasons that farmers have adopted them. Among these four rivers, nitrate currently exceeds the drinking water standard for the largest percent of time in Honey Creek and for the least amount of time in the Maumee River at Waterville.

Although the projected outcome relative to nitrate concentrations exceedence has been met, the reductions in nitrate concentration have likely been caused by multiple factors unrelated to implementation of BMPs associated with this project.

Table 5. Percent of time selected nitrate concentrations are exceeded for Honey Creek, Rock Creek, the Sandusky River and the Maumee River during two time periods.

River	Nitrate-N concentration mg/L	Percent of time nitrate concentration is exceeded	
		2001-06	2008-13
Honey Creek	12	4.4%	1.5%
	10	6.6%	3.0%
	8	11.3%	6.4%
Rock Creek	12	1.3%	0.3%
	10	2.0%	0.6%
	8	3.6%	1.6%
Sandusky	12	4.1%	0.5%
	10	6.7%	2.4%
	8	13.4%	7.1%
Maumee	12	3.4%	0.4%
	10	5.8%	0.9%
	8	11.2%	5.3%

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Appendix 1—Tributary loading station information

See additional information on the NCWQR Website at www.heidelberg.edu/ncwqr.

Station names and location

Station Name
Blanchard River near Findlay OH
Chickasaw Creek at St. Marys, OH
Cuyahoga River at Independence, OH
Great Miami River at Miamisburg, OH
Honey Creek at Melmore, Ohio
Maumee River at Waterville, OH
Muskingum River at McConnelsville, OH
Portage River at Woodville, OH
River Raisin near Monroe, MI
Rock Creek at Tiffin, OH
Sandusky River near Fremont, OH
Scioto River at Chillicothe, OH
Tiffin River at Stryker
Unnamed Tributary to Lost Creek near Farmer, OH (ne of Hicksville)

Appendix Table 1. Network stations in operation through the 2012 WY

Station name	USGS No.	Area, km ²	HUC_8	Years of study*/ Period of Record	LAT_DMS	LON_DMS
Blanchard River near Findlay OH	4189000	895.8	4100008	5 years, 2008-	41°03'21"	83°41'17"
Chickasaw Creek at St. Marys, OH	40291308-4285400	42.5	5120101	4 years, 2009-	40°29'12.8"	84°28'54.2"
Cuyahoga River at Independence, OH	4208000	1,830.3	4110002	31 years 1982-	41°23'43"	81°37'48"
Great Miami River at Miamisburg, OH	3271500	7,018.5	5080002	17 years, 1996-	39°38'40"	84°17'23"
Honey Creek at Melmore, Ohio	4197100	385.7	4100011	37 years 1976-	41°01'20"	83°06'35"
Maumee River at Waterville, OH	4193500	16,387.6	4100006	35 years, 1975-1978, 1982-	41°30'00"	83°42'46"
Muskingum River at McConnellsville, OH	3150000	19,214.7	5040004	19 years, 1994-	39°38'42"	81°51'00"
Portage River at Woodville, OH	4195500	1,108.0	4100010	2 years, 2011-	41°26'58"	83°21'41"
River Raisin near Monroe, MI	4176500	2,697.6	4100002	35 years, 1982-	41°57'38"	83°31'52"
Rock Creek at Tiffin, OH	4197170	89.6	4100011	30 years, 1983-	41°06'49"	83°10'06"
Sandusky River near Fremont, OH	4198000	3,238.7	4100011	38 years, 1975-	41°18'28"	83°09'32"
Scioto River at Chillicothe, OH	3231500	9,964.6	5060002	13 years ² , 1996	39°20'29"	82°58'16"
Tiffin River at Stryker	4185000	1,061.4	4100006	5 years, 2008-	41°30'16"	84°25'47"
Unnamed Tributary to Lost Creek near Farmer, OH (ne of Hicksville)	4185440	11.0	4100009	5 years, 2008	41°21'42"	84°41'28"

² Scioto records incomplete 2009-2011

Appendix Table 2. Land use characteristics of tributary loading watersheds.

Monitoring station	Land use as percent of total watershed area upstream from stream gage.							
	Agriculture	Forest	Grass_Hay_Pasture	Open_Water	Other	Urban	Wetland	Total
Blanchard	78.8	6.3	3.5	0.6	0.1	10.5	0.3	100
Chickasaw	79.0	2.8	8.9	0.0	0.1	9.1	0.0	100
Cuyahoga	9.0	33.6	11.8	2.6	0.4	39.5	3.1	100
Great Miami	64.5	8.6	8.5	1.0	0.1	17.0	0.3	100
Honey Creek	81.1	9.5	2.0	0.3	0.2	6.7	0.2	100
Lost Creek	77.5	7.9	8.6	0.3	0.0	4.3	1.5	100
Maumee	73.3	6.5	6.3	0.7	0.2	10.6	2.3	100
Muskingum	23.6	43.0	18.8	1.2	0.4	12.4	0.5	100
Portage	84.4	4.5	1.3	0.4	0.2	9.0	0.2	100
River Raisin	49.6	11.0	18.7	1.4	0.4	10.8	8.2	100
Rock Creek	71.9	11.4	7.8	0.0	0.0	8.8	0.2	100
Sandusky	77.6	8.8	4.3	0.5	0.3	8.1	0.3	100
Scioto	61.7	10.9	8.6	1.0	0.2	17.3	0.3	100
Tiffin	60.5	8.9	14.8	1.0	0.2	7.5	7.0	100

Appendix Figure 2. Changes in drainage area for the Honey Creek chemical sampling station resulting from movement of station due to bridge construction. The USGS station remained at the downstream location.